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A SECONDARY ANALYSIS OF THE NSQIP DATABASE TO REDUCE ADVERSE
POSTOPERATIVE RESPIRATORY OCCURRENCES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

This project utilized the American College of Surgeons (ACS) National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (NSQIP) database to explore preoperative patient variables as predictors of adverse postoperative respiratory occurrences (APRO) in thoracic surgery patients. These APROs include pulmonary embolism, pneumonia, unplanned intubation, and failure to wean. APROs are a significant problem in patients undergoing thoracic surgery. APROs can result in prolonged lengths of stay, poor long-term and short-term outcomes, and increased healthcare costs for patients and healthcare organizations. Conditional logistic regression explored which preoperative patient variables significantly influenced the odds of observing the APROs. Current Procedural Terminology (CPT) codes were used to match 722 thoracic surgery cases to a control case based on age +/- five years. Each APRO model contained five preoperative patient variables: sex, body mass index (BMI), serum creatinine, serum albumin, and hematocrit. These variables were chosen based on a review of recent literature and data available within the NSQIP database. Preoperative serum albumin was found to be significantly associated with all four APROs, and preoperative hematocrit was found to be significantly associated with three of four APROs (pulmonary embolism, unplanned intubation, and failure to wean). Findings from this project emphasize the need to optimize preoperative serum albumin, serum hematocrit, and serum creatinine at or near normal levels to decrease the odds of observing APROs after thoracic surgery. The authors of this project recommend the creation of checklists or risk assessment tools to preoperatively evaluate patients' risk for developing an APRO after thoracic surgery.

Keywords: adverse postoperative respiratory occurrences, APROs, pulmonary embolism, pneumonia, unplanned intubation, failure to wean, albumin, hematocrit, creatinine, sex, body mass index (BMI), thoracic surgery

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Background

Patients undergoing surgery under general anesthesia will have an anticipated decline in their respiratory status (Bigatello & Pesenti, 2019). Adverse postoperative respiratory occurrence (APRO) is an overarching term that describes a spectrum of respiratory complications that can disturb postoperative pulmonary function. The severity depends on patient and surgical factors (Odor et al., 2020). APROs such as pneumonia, unplanned intubation, pulmonary embolism, and failure to wean are associated with prolonged lengths of stay and poor long-term outcomes (Piccioni et al., 2020; Miskovic & Lumb, 2017). Adverse respiratory occurrences in the postoperative period occur in as many as 49% of all surgical patients and 15–40% of patients after major thoracic surgery (Piccioni et al., 2020). APROs are the primary cause of mortality and morbidity after lung resection, with a mortality rate of 20-50% (Blanc et al., 2018).

Problem Statement

Patients undergoing thoracic surgery are at heightened risk for APROs due to surgical manipulation, retraction, and excision of pulmonary tissue and intercostal muscles that aid in normal respiration (Fuzhi et al., 2022). It is known that thoracic surgery has potential pulmonary complications, with atelectasis and pneumonia occurring in up to 75% of patients (Zhao et al., 2021). Failure to wean from mechanical ventilation after thoracic surgery is another complication that can worsen pulmonary problems among individuals postoperatively. Research findings are inconsistent regarding the number of hours that failure to wean. However, Askoy et al. (2021) described prolonged intubation as > 24 hours. Failure to wean from mechanical ventilation can have both short and long-term complications. Nosocomial infections, prolonged hospital stays, and a significant financial burden are a few adverse effects of prolonged intubation due to failure to wean from mechanical ventilation (Wu et al., 2019).

According to Miskovic and Lumb (2017), APRO increases 30-day patient mortality from 3% to 30%, 90-day mortality from 1.2% to 24.4%, 1-year mortality from 8.7% to 45.9%, and 5-year mortality from 41.1% to 71.4%. Furthermore, APROs can prolong the length of stay (LOS) by as many as 17 days. As a result, healthcare costs are significantly increased (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017). The incremental cost of an APRO was reported at \$25,498 (Fleisher & Linde-Zwirble, 2014). Therefore, preventing APROs may provide life and cost-saving benefits to the patient and healthcare service providers.

Research on what specific perioperative factors contribute the most to APROs following thoracic surgery is scarce. One study identified female gender, leukocytosis, and lactate levels as risk factors that led to prolonged mechanical ventilation in cardiac surgery patients (Aksoy et al., 2021). Another study reported the duration of surgery, body mass index (BMI), smoking, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status score, intraoperative fluid administration, gender, age, and preoperative forced vital capacity after one second as risk factors associated with pulmonary compromise in patients undergoing lung resection surgeries (Kaufmann et al., 2019). A preoperative albumin level of less than 3.8g/dL has been reported to predict postoperative respiratory complications in octogenarian patients undergoing lung resection for malignancy (Saji et al., 2017). In pediatric patients undergoing adenotonsillectomy, red cell distribution width provided meaningful information to assist clinicians with predicting respiratory adverse events (Kozanhan & Iyisoy, 2017). Although this project focused on adult patients, knowledge of factors that lead to APROs in the pediatric population may allow for further risk factors to be identified for adults. Evidence from these studies provides strong implications for predicting the risk for adult patients undergoing thoracic surgery.

There is a need for current research on patient factors, such as preoperative laboratory results, associated with an increased risk of pulmonary compromise after surgery. Early recognition of risk factors that may increase the risk of pulmonary complications after thoracic surgery can prompt providers to implement mitigation strategies and thereby improve patient outcomes and decrease healthcare costs (Garutti et al., 2019). Albumin, blood urea nitrogen (BUN), serum creatinine, liver enzymes, hematocrit, white blood cell count, age, and BMI are identified potential variables that need to be explored.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to conduct a secondary data analysis using the National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (NSQIP) database to analyze patient data to identify specific variables that may be predictors of APROs, including reintubation, pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, and prolonged mechanical ventilation. The first aim was to conduct a secondary analysis of NSQIP data to identify correlations between preoperative albumin, hematocrit, creatinine, BMI, and male gender and the development of an APRO, such as the occurrence of unplanned intubation, pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, and prolonged mechanical ventilation >48 hours, following thoracic surgery. The second aim sought to identify which variables may present as predictors of APROs. The third aim was to create recommendations for future practice based on findings.

Supporting Framework

Background

Titler et al. (1994) first developed the Iowa Model of Research in Practice in 1994. The model at that time was based on the Quality Assurance Model Using Research first presented by Watson et al. in 1987. The Iowa Model is a heuristic approach to quality improvement through

the utilization of nursing research (Titler et al., 1994). Titler et al. (1994) identified that the desire for improvement comes from two primary sources, also known as triggers. Triggers motivate nurses to create changes in practice. These triggers are either repeatedly encountered clinical problems or the introduction of new knowledge (Titler et al., 1994).

Since its inception, the Iowa Model has been revised multiple times to incorporate the wider availability of information and evidence and address the ever-changing healthcare system (Buckwalter et al., 2017; Titler et al., 2001). In 2001, Titler et al. revised the Iowa Model to incorporate new terminology and feedback loops, address changes in the healthcare market, and encourage using other types of evidence when the research was insufficient to direct practice. It was in this revision that model designers began using the phrase "evidence-based practice" (EBP) instead of "research-based practice." Doing so acknowledged that research may not always be available or conclusive enough to guide practice (Titler et al., 2001).

More recently, the Iowa Model was revised and validated again by the Iowa Model Collaborative (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The Iowa Model Collaborative utilized literature, user feedback, and collaborative member experiences to identify challenges, assess utility, and generate suggestions for revisions. The Iowa Model-Revised was created and presented for further refinement and validation at the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics' 22nd National EBP Conference in 2015. This conference resulted in the form of the Iowa Model presently in use (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

Duff et al. (2020) point out that this model is meant for use by nurses. However, the model can be interdisciplinary, and nurses can lead direct change processes. The Iowa Model also includes assessing the proposed change's priority before proceeding to ensure the organization acknowledges a need for change (Duff et al., 2020). The Iowa Model ties in the

ability of nurses to make direct evidence-based change while gaining support from supporting stakeholders and the organization (Duff et al., 2020).

Clinical Examples

The Iowa Model has been used to guide the development and implementation of multiple evidence-based projects that resulted in practice changes that improved patient outcomes. For example, a team of nurses utilized the Iowa Model to create a practice change by constructing and establishing a process to infuse 3% NaCl safely through peripheral intravenous access as opposed to requiring a central line for infusion, which is associated with severe risk factors (Jannotta et al., 2021). The practice change minimized adverse events by avoiding inserting central lines using an adequate peripheral IV to infuse 3% NaCl (Jannotta et al., 2021). The Iowa Model was used to guide a practice change involving the use of dexmedetomidine in the pediatric intensive care unit to provide long-term sedation in non-intubated patients (Fannon et al., 2021). Implementation of this project helped provide safe sedation to children in the intensive care unit (Fannon et al., 2021). A third study utilized the Iowa Model to assess if parents at the bedside benefit when their child is immediately brought to the recovery unit after having general anesthesia (Hanrahan et al., 2019). Following the steps of the Iowa Model, the study found that it is advantageous to have pre-educated and prepared parents at the bedside when children arrive at the recovery room (Hanrahan et al., 2019). All these studies went through each step of the Iowa Model to successfully implement an EBP change.

Iowa Model Steps

The Iowa Model Revised (Appendix A) provided a framework that was utilized to guide this specific project. The Iowa Model, which consists of seven steps with three decision points,

guided the development and implementation of this EBP Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project. Each individual step will be discussed below and how it is applied to this project.

Identify Triggering Issues/Opportunities

Triggers are a concept used to help create a change in practice and promote nurses' critical thinking (Titler et al., 2001). Postoperative pulmonary complications were identified as the trigger for this project. As pulmonary complications occur in almost 50% of patients in the postoperative period after major thoracic surgery, it was determined that this issue needed further investigation (M. Gabot DNP, CRNA, FAANA, personal communication, August 2022).

State the Question or Purpose

Based on the Iowa Model Revised, after identifying a triggering issue, the project's purpose needed to be stated (Titler et al., 2001). For this project, the purpose was to conduct a secondary data analysis using the NSQIP database to identify risk factors (predictors) that may contribute to APROs, which include reintubation, pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, and prolonged mechanical ventilation. This purpose was created based on a clinically identified issue in a thoracic surgery quality improvement meeting at a large regional hospital.

Identification of Topic as a Priority

The first decision point in the Iowa Model revised is to determine if the selected problem for the project is a priority for the organization (Titler et al., 2001). This is a crucial step as it determines whether resources will be provided to support the implementation of the project. The topic must be prioritized for the project to move forward. If it is not seen as a priority, according to the Iowa Model, the next logical step would be to consider an alternative issue to research. The Kaiser Permanente organization believes that quality healthcare includes ensuring the safety of its members (Kaiser Permanente Quality, Risk Management & Patient Safety Department,

2018). Every year, Kaiser Permanente outlines priorities and goals and develops, tests, and implements new programs designed to improve patient safety. Reducing the risk of surgical complications is a patient safety goal that Kaiser Permanente has identified (Kaiser Permanente Quality, Risk Management & Patient Safety Department, 2018).

Similarly, a core value of the Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA) is promoting excellence in the field of anesthesia to improve the care of the individual (KPSA, 2022). Furthermore, KPSA believes that developing research skills in its students will help expand the nursing profession's knowledge base and positively affect the whole healthcare delivery system (KPSA, 2022). The project team had the support of KPSA and the medical center in San Bernardino County, which facilitated access to the NSQIP database to research this topic. Therefore, the topic of APROs in thoracic surgical patients was seen as a priority, thus allowing for the advancement to the next steps of the Iowa Model.

Form a Team

Typically, forming a team comes after an issue is identified and the topic is deemed a priority. However, in the case of this project, the circumstances dictated that a team be formed at the start of the project to best align with the academic course. The team for a project is responsible for developing, implementing, and evaluating the evidence-based project (Titler et al., 2001). The team for this project consisted of three students pursuing their DNP degrees: Malia Case, BSN, R.N.; Abby Schrader, BSN, R.N.; and Evan Shmagranoff, BSN, R.N., a project leader: Dr. Mark Gabot, DNP, CRNA, FAANA as well as a faculty team member: Dr. Sadeeka Al-Majid, PhD, R.N., FAAN.

Assemble, Appraise, and Synthesize Body of Evidence

The next step in the Revised Iowa Model is to research the best available evidence using

evidence-based guidelines, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and clinical studies (Titler et al., 2001). Our group conducted an exhaustive review of the literature concerning postoperative pulmonary complications in thoracic surgery patients to understand better what risk factors are currently known and what risk factors are worth further studying. A search for relevant articles was conducted using PubMed, ProQuest, CINAHL, and EBSCO databases. Search terms included: adverse respiratory occurrence, postoperative pulmonary complications, pulmonary complications, adverse respiratory complications, predictors, laboratory values, open thoracic surgery, closed thoracic surgery, thoracic surgery, respiratory problems, complications, prolonged intubation, albumin, BUN, serum creatinine, liver enzymes, hematocrit, white blood cell count, age, and BMI.

Evaluate Sufficiency of Evidence

The second decision point in the Iowa Model is determining if sufficient evidence is available to support the implementation of the project. If it is found that there is insufficient evidence on the topic, either a new study must be conducted or other types of evidence, such as case reports, expert opinions, scientific principles, or theory, to create updated guidelines of practice (Titler et al., 2001). This step comes directly after critically appraising and synthesizing current evidence. The literature review conducted for this project allowed for the determination that there is enough existing evidence to proceed with the next steps of the Iowa Model. It was determined from the literature review that there was sufficient evidence regarding what factors may lead to APROs in multiple patient populations. However, more evidence was required to determine specific risk factors that result in APROs in the thoracic surgery patient. The literature review identified insufficient research on lab values and the potential correlations with pulmonary outcomes after thoracic surgery, thus signifying the need for this EBP project.

Design and Pilot the Practice

Piloting the change in practice should consist of six steps: select the outcomes to be achieved, collect baseline data, develop an EBP guideline, implement the guideline in a small controlled setting, evaluate the process, and modify the guideline based on outcome data (Titler et al., 2001). For this DNP project, recommendations for adoption to practice have been formulated and presented in the Discussions section of this document.

Disseminate Results

The Iowa Model's last step is disseminating the project's findings. The findings from the study yielded significant data. The results of this EBP project will be communicated through multiple methods. Examples include a typed manuscript that will be submitted to the International Student Journal of Nurse Anesthesia, a poster that can be presented at a California State University Fullerton (CSUF) College of Health and Human Development Student Research Showcase, and a podium presentation at the Kaiser Permanente Nurse Anesthetist Association 2024 Winter Conference. The team's goal will be to disseminate the results to as many healthcare providers as possible. The Iowa Model has been proven to guide EBP projects to success, which is why this framework was chosen for this EBP project (Duff et al., 2020). The proposed project was an evidence-based plan, and the Iowa Model helped navigate the project in the right direction while ensuring stakeholder support. Individual steps were laid out in the model and were followed as closely as possible to achieve the best chance of success. This framework provided a guide for this project based on the above information.

Review of Literature

Overview

A literature review was performed to determine the most current knowledge of APROs following thoracic surgery. Identifying associated risk factors and predictors of APROs guided the secondary analysis of the NSQIP database. A search for relevant articles was conducted using PubMed, ProQuest, CINAHL, and EBSCO databases. Search terms included: adverse respiratory occurrence, postoperative pulmonary complications, pulmonary complications, adverse respiratory complications, predictors, laboratory values, open thoracic surgery, closed thoracic surgery, thoracic surgery, respiratory problems, complications, prolonged intubation, albumin, BUN, serum creatinine, liver enzymes, hematocrit, white blood cell count, age, and BMI. Due to the scarcity of research in this area, the search was expanded to include the pediatric population and literature published between 2015 and 2022. The search was limited to articles published in English and peer-reviewed journals.

This literature review addressed commonalities, themes, and inconsistencies in the current literature. The search identified a total of nineteen studies. Out of the studies investigated, eleven studies explored thoracic surgical procedures, three in general surgery, and five investigated miscellaneous surgeries. Six studies were prospective cohort studies, three were systematic reviews, nine were retrospective analysis studies, and one was a randomized controlled trial (RCT). The studies used in this literature review are the highest levels of evidence available, given the nature of this topic and the population being studied.

Additionally, a systematic review was included for every surgical type subsection in this review. The included studies covered a wide variety of patient demographic, clinical, and surgical factors. This allowed for a better generalization of thoracic surgery patients. Many of the

studies that were incorporated in the review had produced statistically significant results regarding the association between APROs and lactate levels, albumin, forced expiratory volume (FEV1), partial pressure of oxygen (PaO₂), and male gender (Aksoy et al., 2021; Kaufmann et al., 2019; Saji et al., 2017). One downfall to some studies presented in this review is that they provided conflicting results concerning the value of laboratory tests in predicting APROs, such as an observational study by Blanc et al. (2018), who reported FEV1 as an insignificant predictor of APROs. These inconsistencies could be attributed to variations in methodologies and small sample sizes. The limitations in these studies support the need for further research on this topic and establish a genuine need for this project.

Guidelines that help predict APROs in thoracic surgery patients are imperative to minimize any significant risks to these patients in the perioperative period. APROs can also put a financial strain on the hospital. One study found that a cost upwards of \$7,303 can accrue per APRO developed by a patient (Fleisher & Linde-Zwirble, 2014). Based on this, predictive risk factors can be used to prevent APROs, thus releasing the financial strain on the hospital tied to APROs. In addition to financial burdens, APROs are also shown to increase mortality rates and LOS in postoperative patients (Blanc et al., 2018). APROs have also been documented to cause significant problems in healthcare, and the benefits of predicting these complications in advance can substantially impact patients.

Pulmonary Complications in Thoracic Surgery

Multiple studies have identified certain risk factors for APROs after thoracic surgery (Aksoy et al., 2021; Kaufmann et al., 2019; Saji et al., 2017). In a retrospective observational study, Fernandez-Bustamante et al. (2017) found that despite maintaining the currently recommended intraoperative ventilation strategies, APROs still occurred after non-cardiothoracic

surgeries. This indicates that current practice needs to be improved to decrease the incidence of APROs. Recent evidence suggests that lactate levels, albumin, FEV1, PaO2, and male gender can all be risk factors for developing APROs after thoracic surgery (Aksoy et al., 2021; Kaufmann et al., 2019; Saji et al., 2017). However, Blanc et al. (2018) reported preoperative FEV1 as an insignificant predictor of APROs. This inconsistency emphasized the need for further research in this area. Furthermore, much of the current knowledge regarding the aforementioned risk factors came from retrospective observational studies, which do not provide the highest level of evidence.

Certain ventilator settings may also predispose patients to APROs (Marret et al., 2018). Specifically, utilizing lung protective ventilation such as low tidal volumes and adding positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) during surgery can decrease the incidence of pulmonary complications such as bronchial obstruction, bronchial fistula, atelectasis, pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, acute respiratory failure, and hypercapnia (Marret et al., 2018). An RCT conducted by Marret et al. (2018) compared the use of high tidal volume (10ml/kg) and no PEEP with low tidal volume (5ml/kg) with PEEP and found a 51% reduction of major pulmonary complications in the group that received low tidal volumes with PEEP. Walsh et al. (2022) conducted a systematic review in which patients from both the intensive care unit and operating room were included. No clinically significant differences between the use of high or low tidal volumes were identified.

Frailty is associated with increased APROs in elderly patients (Buitrago et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2022). One prospective study used the frailty of patients undergoing video-assisted thoracoscopic pulmonary resections to predict APROs (Chen et al., 2022). Frailty was defined using the fatigue, resistance, ambulation, illness, and weight loss (FRAIL) scale (Chen et al.,

2022). Patients deemed frail were about six times more likely to have APROs after surgery (Chen et al., 2022). This result is strengthened by a study conducted by Buitrago et al. (2018) in which patients undergoing a tracheobronchoplasty were noted to have higher rates of major respiratory complications when identified as frail. These studies can be referenced by comparing a patient's frailty to their metabolic equivalent (MET) level and ASA physical status. It can be valuable to look further into the MET level and ASA physical status in patients undergoing thoracic procedures and observe if there is any correlation between these preoperative patient factors and APROs.

Preoperative laboratory values have also been associated with APROs (Ruan et al., 2021; Burton et al., 2018; Li et al., 2018). Burton et al. (2018) examined 16,696 patients who underwent lung resection; 593 patients experienced unplanned intubation postoperatively. Burton et al. (2018) concluded that patients who experienced unplanned intubation were more likely to have lower preoperative albumin and hematocrit and higher preoperative serum creatinine. Li et al. (2018) found that patients undergoing thoracic surgery for lung cancer were approximately 15% more likely to experience APRO if their serum albumin was decreased.

Similarly, Ruan et al. (2021) found that in patients undergoing pneumonectomy, postoperative complications occurred more frequently in patients with a BMI <25 and a decreased serum albumin level. Serum albumin, hematocrit, and creatinine are known predictors of postoperative complications in general and respiratory failure, hemorrhage, heart failure, and infection (Ruan et al., 2021).

Research revealed there is a risk of developing an APRO after thoracic surgery. Albumin, creatinine, hematocrit, and frailty were variables in the literature review that exhibited similar outcomes in that there was a correlation with developing an APRO (Buitrago et al., 2018; Burton

et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2022; Li et al., 2018; Ruan et al., 2021). However, ventilator settings and FEV1 scores differed between studies (Aksoy et al., 2021; Blanc et al., 2018; Fernandez-Bustamante et al., 2017; Marret et al., 2018; Kaufmann et al., 2019; Saji et al., 2017; Walsh et al., 2022). Current research was lacking overall regarding their implication in all types of APROs, such as pneumonia, unplanned intubation, pulmonary embolism, and failure to wean. Given this result, a secondary analysis using the NSQIP database aimed to contribute valuable information in evaluating whether certain variables, previously found in literature, held significance in correlation to APROs.

Pulmonary Complications in General Surgery

Preoperative anemia and hypoalbuminemia have been well-established as predictors for generalized adverse perioperative outcomes in general surgery (Muñoz et al., 2017; Fowler et al., 2015). Preoperative anemia is common in approximately 36% of general surgery patients (Muñoz et al., 2017). A meta-analysis that involved 949,445 patients undergoing major elective surgery showed that anemia was associated with increased in-hospital and 30-day mortality (Fowler et al., 2015). Gebeyehu et al. (2022) determined that if a patient's serum albumin was <3.5 g/dL, they were 23 times more likely to develop APRO. However, mirroring current research in thoracic surgery, research regarding serum albumin and APRO was limited to smaller, single-center studies (Gebeyehu et al., 2022). As there seems to be significance in the literature regarding anemia and albumin as they correlate to APROs, the NSQIP database holds valuable data that was analyzed and may be useful for future practices.

Pulmonary Complications in Miscellaneous Surgery/Intensive Care Units

Similar to research conducted in general surgery, perioperative anemia and hypoalbuminemia are predictors of adverse postoperative outcomes (Bouchard et al., 2021;

Wang et al., 2021). Bouchard et al. (2021) found that preoperative anemia was associated with a significant increase in serious postoperative complications such as pneumonia, unplanned intubation, and pulmonary embolism in patients undergoing gynecologic surgery. In this population, anemia increased the odds of serious postoperative complications by 38%. Similarly, Wang et al. (2021) found that anemic patients undergoing orthopedic surgery are more likely to experience general postoperative complications. The odds of adverse postoperative outcomes double as a patient progresses from mild to moderate to severe anemia (Wang et al., 2021). Furthermore, patients with severe anemia were more likely to experience APRO (Wang et al., 2021). Lastly, a systematic review of spinal surgery patients found low preoperative hemoglobin and hematocrit significantly associated with postoperative complications and increased LOS (Suresh et al., 2022). Low serum albumin was also a predictor of postoperative complications in patients undergoing spinal surgery (Jiang et al., 2022). These results reflected the aforementioned research in general and thoracic surgery, underscoring the importance of strongly establishing hypoalbuminemia as a predictive factor for APRO and that anemia was associated with poorer outcomes postoperatively.

Although this project focused on the risk factors and predictors of APROs, specifically in patients undergoing thoracic surgery, the synthesis of evidence on predictors of APROs from other surgeries provided insight into factors that should be studied further in the thoracic surgery patient. The literature suggested that in the thoracic surgery patient, frailty (Chen et al., 2022; Buitrago et al., 2018), low BMI (Ruan et al., 2021; Kaufmann et al., 2019), gender (Saji et al., 2017; Burton et al., 2018), lactate levels (Aksoy et al., 2021), FEV1, PaO2 (Kaufmann et al., 2019), and high tidal volumes (Marret et al., 2018) are all potential risk factors for developing APROs. Perioperative anemia (Ruan et al., 2021; Saji et al., 2017; Burton et al., 2018; Li et al.,

2018), hypoalbuminemia (Ruan et al., 2021; Burton et al., 2018; Li et al., 2018), and elevated serum creatinine (Burton et al., 2018) are predictors for increased perioperative morbidity in thoracic surgery patients; however, research was lacking regarding their predictive value for pneumonia, unplanned intubation, pulmonary embolism, and failure to wean in this population. In general surgery, anemia and hypoalbuminemia were primary indicators associated with adverse perioperative outcomes (Fowler et al., 2015; Gebeyehu et al., 2022). Additionally, research has shown that anemia and hypoalbuminemia were factors for increased postoperative morbidity in miscellaneous surgeries (Bouchard et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2021; Suresh et al., 2022). As stated in earlier sections, there is great importance in detecting risk factors for APROs in surgical patients. These benefits include decreasing morbidity and mortality rates, decreasing the LOS for patients, and decreasing financial costs for both the patient and the hospital. The benefits this project can produce for patients and hospitals need to be recognized, as it can have a major impact on the care of surgical patients.

As noted earlier, some inconsistencies exist among current studies regarding the value of laboratory tests in predicting risks for APROs. These inconsistencies could be attributed to variations in methodologies and sample sizes used in these studies. These limitations emphasized the need for further research in this area. By identifying laboratory values and other factors that might predict the risk for APROs, this DNP project may provide data to guide the early identification of patients at risk of APROs, ultimately improving patient outcomes.

The NSQIP registry serves as a repository of data from more than 300 hospitals that involve care and outcomes from a surgical standpoint and tracks patient data for up to 30 days postoperatively (Zhong et al., 2022). The NSQIP database was used to identify correlations between preoperative APROs and patient factors, including albumin, hematocrit, creatinine,

BMI, and male gender. This study aimed to formulate recommendations for best practices among non-cardiac thoracic surgery patients.

Methods

There was a need for current research on patient factors, such as preoperative laboratory results, associated with an increased risk of pulmonary compromise after thoracic surgery. The comprehensive literature review identified gaps in existing knowledge related to factors that may contribute to APRO. This project addressed these gaps through three specific aims. The first aim was to conduct a secondary data analysis using the American College of Surgeons (ACS) NSQIP database to identify a potential correlation between preoperative albumin, hematocrit, creatinine, BMI, and male gender and the occurrence of unplanned intubation, pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, and prolonged mechanical ventilation >48 hours postoperatively in patients undergoing thoracic surgery. The second aim was to identify which variables may predict each APRO. The third aim was to create practice recommendations based on analysis findings. Identifying correlations between these factors and establishing which are predictors should help prevent the occurrence of APROs in this patient population. Early recognition of risk factors that may increase the risk of pulmonary complications after thoracic surgery and their management can improve patient outcomes and decrease healthcare costs (Garutti et al., 2019). The methods section provides detailed descriptions of the methodology and procedures used to achieve the above-stated specific aims, and a plan for evaluating the achievement of the project's aims (Appendix B, Table 2).

Design

The design of this project was a retrospective analysis of NSQIP data. The benefits of doing a retrospective analysis include identifying potential risk factors through already existing data. The NSQIP database contains a vast amount of diverse patient data, which provided a large sample size and, in return, allowed the results to be more generalizable (Grove & Gray, 2019). A

retrospective analysis is beneficial when conducting initial research and can be used to support future studies (Grove & Gray, 2019). This study will lay the groundwork for future DNP projects. The primary purpose for utilizing a retrospective analysis for this study was to provide the best methodology for determining risk factors in a specific population. Given the nature of this study, a retrospective analysis is the highest level of evidence that can be done ethically. However, the limitations of retrospective studies are the use of convenience sampling and the potential for confounding (Grove & Gray, 2019). This project used extensive inclusion and exclusion criteria to control these limitations (Grove & Gray, 2019).

Setting

NSQIP data, collected from multiple sites in the United States, was analyzed and interpreted to provide practice recommendations for thoracic surgery patients at a facility of interest.

Sample

To provide accurate data for this retrospective analysis, data collected from adult patients (18 years or older) who underwent either closed or open thoracic surgery that is non-emergent were included; included cases were based on Current Procedural Terminology (CPT) codes for thoracic surgery (Appendix C). Non-emergent and emergent procedures were defined and differentiated as procedures where consent could be given versus life-threatening conditions in which consent could not be given. Data from pediatric patients (younger than 18 years) and patients who underwent cardiac surgeries or emergent procedures was excluded. The NSQIP database utilizes its own extensive exclusion criteria for cases included within the database and hospitals that may contribute to the data pool (ACS, 2022a). Minor cases, patients less than 18 years, patients with an ASA score of 6, cases involving Hyperthermic Intraperitoneal

Chemotherapy (HIPEC), trauma cases, any patient who is admitted to the hospital and has a transplant procedure or any surgery thereafter, cases beyond three per 8-day sampling cycle for inguinal herniorrhaphies, breast lumpectomies, laparoscopic cholecystectomies, transurethral resections of prostates and transurethral resections of bladder tumors, cases beyond the required number for each cycle, surgeries related to a complication of a prior procedure, and any patient who already had a NSQIP-assessed procedure within the previous 30 days are all excluded from the NSQIP database.

This project aimed to determine risk factors and predictors for APROs in thoracic surgery patients. Therefore, there needed to be strict inclusion and exclusion criteria for the studied data to provide the best data points and the highest level of internal validity (Grove & Gray, 2019). Additionally, a large sample size allowed for more generalizable results, thus increasing external validity (Grove & Gray, 2019). Assuring high internal and external validity allows for reproducibility, results more reflective of reality and not influenced by extraneous variables, and results that can be used effectively to form practice recommendations that will benefit the greatest number of people (Grove & Gray, 2019).

For this project's sample, there was a time limit set for the data; only 2021 NSQIP data was included. Therefore, only data was collected that met the inclusion and exclusion criteria, as well as data that provided information regarding preoperative albumin, hematocrit, creatinine, BMI, and gender, and the occurrence of unplanned intubation, pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, and prolonged mechanical ventilation >48 hours postoperatively in patients undergoing thoracic surgery. An initial database review determined that 6,331 thoracic surgery cases were included in 2021. Of that number, only the 722 patients who experienced an APRO were included in this

secondary data analysis. Furthermore, we extracted an equal or greater number of matched control cases.

Ethical Considerations

Approval of the Institutional Review Boards (IRB) at KPSA and CSUF was obtained before initiating data collection from the NSQIP database. Given that the project was a retrospective analysis of existing de-identified patient data, there was no perceived risk of violating the Health Information Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA). Furthermore, because the information is de-identified within the NSQIP database, it is exempt from consent requirements. Lastly, all NSQIP data for our study was kept on a secured, password-encrypted hard drive, accessible only by authorized investigators included in the IRB application.

Conducting this project was approved by the faculty Team Leader and Team Member from CSUF and KPSA in December 2022 (Appendix B, Table 1). This project was approved by the KPSA CSUF IRB in 2023. The data collected for this project was analyzed in the second and third quarters of 2023, and the results of this project and resulting practice recommendations will be presented in December 2023.

Data Collection

NSQIP Database. The NSQIP database is a multicenter, nationally validated, risk-adjusted, outcomes-oriented program that measures and improves surgical care quality (ACS, 2022a). It was first created in 1994 by the Department of Veterans Affairs (V.A.) after the success of the National V.A. Surgical Risk Study (NVASRS) (ACS, 2022a). The original database was based on the theories of Lisa Iezzoni, who believed that healthcare outcomes could be described by examining patient factors, effectiveness of care, and random variation (ACS, 2022a). By reviewing the NSQIP database and focusing on improving surgical outcomes, V.A.

hospitals achieved a 47 percent decrease in postoperative mortality and a 43 percent decrease in morbidity rates from 1991 to 2006 (ACS, 2022a).

In 1999, a pilot study was performed to determine the applicability of risk-adjustment models used by the NSQIP database to heterogeneous private-sector hospitals and the feasibility of implementing the NSQIP database within the private sector. This study found that the data collection methods and the predictive and risk-adjustment models of NSQIP applied to non-V.A. facilities (ACS, 2022a). In 2001, ACS implemented a pilot program to demonstrate that NSQIP also reduced morbidity and mortality in the private sector (ACS, 2022a). Since then, the ACS has continued to add reporting facilities to the database. The ACS NSQIP database currently contains over 150 variables from over 600 participating hospitals for patients undergoing inpatient and outpatient surgeries (ACS, 2022b). The database for 2021 contains 983,851 cases submitted from 685 sites (ACS, 2022b).

A site-specific Surgical Clinical Reviewer (SCR) collects data for each participating facility through multiple methods, including abstraction from patient charts (ACS, 2022b). High-quality data extraction is ensured by multiple methods, including the performance of Inter-Rater Reliability (IRR) audits of chosen participating sites and audits of operating room logs (ACS, 2022b). Additionally, NSQIP utilizes a sampling process called the 8-day cycle for larger institutions that may have the potential for sampling bias. The 8-day cycle results in an equal chance of cases being selected from each day of the week (ACS, 2022b). For our project, all thoracic surgeries were identified and extracted from the NSQIP database by primary surgical procedure.

CPT Codes. CPT codes are five-digit numeric or alphanumeric codes that designate a medical, surgical, radiology, laboratory, anesthesiology, genomic sequencing, or evaluation and

management service or procedure (American Medical Association, 2023); this allows for a standardized and accurate means of communication among a variety of healthcare stakeholders, such as healthcare research, claims processing, and utilization (Dotson, 2013). CPT codes have been designated by the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services as a national coding set and are nationally the most widely accepted medical nomenclature.

The CPT Editorial Panel creates, edits, and maintains CPT codes. The panel members are expert volunteers from various healthcare backgrounds and are appointed by the AMA Board of Trustees (American Medical Association, 2023). The panel meets three times per year to review existing codes and applications for new codes. Code changes made by the panel must meet specific criteria and undergo evidence-based review (American Medical Association, 2023).

Data Analysis and Evaluation

The authors of this scholarly DNP project performed a secondary data analysis of data extracted from the NSQIP database. The analysis explored correlations between preoperative albumin, hematocrit, creatinine, BMI, and gender and the development of one of the four APROs: unplanned intubation, pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, and failure to wean from mechanical ventilation following thoracic surgery. The five variables included for each APRO model were selected based on the literature review and were among the 260 items collected by NSQIP per case. 6,331 thoracic surgery cases were included in the data analysis and extracted from NSQIP. Each APRO case was matched 1:1 with a control (non-APRO case) based on age (+/- 5 years) and CPT code. Conditional logistic regression was performed using the set (model), five predictors for each APRO.

A variance inflation factor analysis was performed to assess the correlation between the independent variables of preoperative albumin, hematocrit, creatinine, BMI, and gender and the

dependent variables of APROs. Multivariate logistic regression was utilized to assess whether the identified variables were predictors of APROs. In general, logistic regression can be used to determine factors that are thought to influence the rate of occurrence of a specific outcome (Tolles & Meurer, 2016). Furthermore, logistic regression can show which of the independent variables has the strongest association with the occurrence of APRO and provide a measure of the potential influence of the variable (Tolles & Meurer, 2016). In other words, logistic regression can show which independent variables within a model are significant predictors of the APRO occurrence, the direction of the relationship, and the change in odds of occurrence relative to a one-unit increase in the predictor value (e.g., odds ratio). Conditional logistic regression was chosen for its ability to adjust results based on confounding factors. This leads to a decreased likelihood of data distortion. Logistic regression has been demonstrated to be very efficient and produces well-calibrated probabilities that are easier to use and implement clinically (Tolles & Meurer, 2016). The project team used different spreadsheets catered to each step during data collection and analysis. For example, we used the logistic regression output table of results to organize the data and results of our logistic regression.

The primary limitations of logistic regression, as related to this study, are the suitability and potential collinearity of the independent variables. Given that this study was limited to the availability of factors measured by the NSQIP database, not all biologically relevant factors to APRO may be included. The collinearity of independent variables may also provide variation in the data, influencing the odds attributed to one factor versus the other. However, the number and type of independent variables in this study were chosen with these limitations in mind.

Results

The 2021 Participant Use Data file available for the ACS NSQIP database contained 260 HIPAA-compliant variables on 983,851 cases submitted from 685 sites in 2021. The cases included were based on CPT codes for the "Surgical Specialty" "Thoracic" surgery (Appendix C). Cases were excluded if the case acuity was "Emergent" or if "Lab value not obtained" or "No response" was entered for any of the following independent variables: gender, height (inches), weight (pounds), preoperative serum creatinine (mg/dL), preoperative serum albumin (g/dL), and preoperative hematocrit (%). Using this and the previously mentioned inclusion and exclusion criteria, 6,331 thoracic cases were identified as eligible for analysis. BMI was calculated using the imperial unit formula (weight/height squared x 703) for each thoracic case. Analysis of the data determined that 722 cases (11% of all thoracic cases) experienced an occurrence of pulmonary embolism ($n = 35$), pneumonia ($n = 382$), unplanned intubation ($n = 151$), or failure to wean ($n = 154$). Each APRO case was matched 1:1 with a control case from all thoracic cases based on age (± 5 years) and CPT code. The reference category for each APRO was "No complication." Furthermore, for the independent variable "gender," the reference category is "female."

Conditional logistic regression was performed for each APRO to explore whether models containing independent variables (predictors) predict categorical outcomes (APRO occurrence) (SAS 9.4 software, 2013). Logistic regression indicates the relative importance of each predictor variable.

Five independent variables, gender, BMI, preoperative serum creatinine (mg/dL), preoperative serum albumin (g/dL), and preoperative hematocrit (%) were entered in the conditional regression model. The assumption of the absence of multicollinearity was examined.

Variance Inflation Factors (VIFs) were calculated to detect the presence of multicollinearity between predictors. High VIFs indicate increased effects of multicollinearity in the model. VIFs greater than five are cause for concern, whereas VIFs of ten should be considered the maximum upper limit (Menard, 2009). All five predictors in the regression model have VIFs less than five, indicating a state of low correlations or associations among the set of predictor variables.

Pulmonary Embolism

The 35 cases of pulmonary embolism represented 0.55% of all thoracic cases and 4.85% of all APROs. The full model containing all five independent variables (predictors) was statistically significant, $\chi^2(5) = 12, p < .05$, suggesting that gender, BMI, preoperative serum creatinine (mg/dL), preoperative serum albumin (g/dL), and preoperative hematocrit (%) had a significant effect on the odds of observing pulmonary embolism. The model as a whole explained 19% (R-square) of the variance in pulmonary embolism occurrence. The effect of preoperative albumin was significant, $B = -1.38, OR = .25, p < .05$, indicating that a one-unit (g/dL) increase in preoperative albumin decreases the odds of observing pulmonary embolism by 75%. The effect of preoperative hematocrit was significant, $B = .22, OR = 1.25, p < .05$, indicating that a one-unit (%) increase in preoperative hematocrit increases the odds of observing pulmonary embolism by 25%. The effects of gender (male), BMI, and preoperative creatinine were not statistically significant, indicating that these independent variables did not significantly affect the odds of pulmonary embolism occurrence.

Pneumonia

The 382 cases of pneumonia represented 6.03% of all thoracic cases and 52.91% of all APROs. Conditional logistic regression was performed to examine whether the independent variables (predictors) significantly affected the odds of pneumonia occurrence. The full model

containing all five independent variables (predictors) was statistically significant, $\chi^2(5) = 41.75$, $p < .0001$, suggesting that sex, BMI, preoperative serum creatinine (mg/dL), preoperative serum albumin (g/dL), and preoperative hematocrit (%) had a significant effect on the odds of observing pneumonia. The model as a whole explained 4% (R-square) of the variance in pneumonia occurrence. The effect of preoperative serum albumin was significant, $B = -.58$, $OR = .56$, $p < .0001$, indicating that a one-unit (g/dL) increase in preoperative albumin decreases the odds of observing pneumonia by 44%. The effects of gender (male), BMI, preoperative serum creatinine, and preoperative hematocrit were not statistically significant, indicating that these independent variables did not significantly affect the odds of pneumonia occurrence.

Unplanned Intubation

The 151 cases of unplanned intubation represented 2.39% of all thoracic cases and 20.91% of all APROs. The full model containing all five independent variables (predictors) was statistically significant, $\chi^2(5) = 28.28$, $p < .0001$, suggesting that gender, BMI, preoperative serum creatinine (mg/dL), preoperative serum albumin (g/dL), and preoperative hematocrit (%) had a significant effect on the odds of observing unplanned intubation. The model as a whole explained 8% (R-square) of the variance in unplanned intubation occurrence. The effect of gender (male) was significant, $B = .64$, $OR = 1.89$, $p < .05$, indicating that male gender increased the odds of observing unplanned intubation by 89%. Preoperative serum creatinine was significant, $B = .45$, $OR = 1.57$, $p < .05$, indicating that a one-unit (mg/dL) increase in preoperative serum creatinine increases the odds of observing unplanned intubation by 57%. Preoperative serum albumin was significant, $B = -.8$, $OR = .45$, $p < .05$, indicating that a one-unit (g/dL) increase in preoperative serum albumin decreases the odds of observing unplanned intubation by 55%. The effect of preoperative hematocrit was significant, $B = -.06$, $OR = .95$, $p <$

.05, indicating that a one-unit (%) increase in preoperative hematocrit decreased the odds of observing unplanned intubation by 5%. The effect of BMI was not statistically significant, indicating that this independent variable did not significantly affect the odds of unplanned intubation occurrence.

Failure to Wean

The 154 cases of failure to wean represented 2.43% of all thoracic cases and 21.33% of all APROs. The full model containing all five independent variables (predictors) was statistically significant, $\chi^2(5) = 27.28, p < .0001$, suggesting that gender, BMI, preoperative serum creatinine (mg/dL), preoperative serum albumin (g/dL), and preoperative hematocrit (%) had a significant effect on the odds of observing failure to wean. The model as a whole explained 7% (R-square) of the variance in failure to wean occurrence. The effect of preoperative serum albumin was significant, $B = -.53, OR = .59, p < .05$, indicating that a one-unit (g/dL) increase in preoperative serum albumin decreases the odds of failure to wean by 41%. The effect of preoperative hematocrit was significant, $B = -.08, OR = .92, p < .05$, indicating that a one-unit (%) increase in preoperative hematocrit decreases the odds of observing failure to wean by 8%. The effects of gender, BMI, and preoperative serum creatinine were not statistically significant, indicating that these independent variables did not significantly affect the odds of failure to wean.

Discussion

The development of APROs occurred in 11% of all thoracic cases. This finding is more than double the incidence of postoperative respiratory complications (5%) observed in a broad, heterogeneous surgical population but less than the 15–40% cited after major thoracic surgery (Piccioni et al., 2020). This discrepancy may be due to using a single ACS NSQIP database year for analysis, as compared to using multiple years.

The full model was significant for each APRO. In addition, all APROs were found to have at least one significant predictor. The occurrence of a pulmonary embolism after thoracic surgery decreased 75% with an increase in preoperative albumin by one-unit (g/dL) ($p < .05$). Conversely, increased preoperative hematocrit by one-unit (%) increased risk by 25% ($p < .05$). Our initial review of the literature found that low hematocrit increases the risk for development of an APRO in general. However, our data analysis found that an increased hematocrit was associated with a heightened risk for a pulmonary embolism specifically. One study, found after our literature review and NSQIP data analysis was complete, reported a venous thromboembolism (VTE) hazard ratio >2 in patients with high hematocrit who had cancer, major trauma, marked immobility, or had recently undergone surgery (Folsom et al., 2020). The increased concentration of blood components can increase blood viscosity and cause venous hemostasis; this, combined with disruptions in the endothelial surface of blood vessels, such as in surgical inflammation, increases the risk of VTE, such as pulmonary embolism and deep vein thrombosis (Hall & Hall, 2021).

Development of pneumonia decreased by 44% for every one-unit (g/dL) increase of preoperative albumin ($p < .0001$). The literature supports this finding and can be attributed to

possible malnutrition, fragility, and decreased physiological reserve in patients undergoing thoracic surgery who can have impaired respiratory function perioperatively.

Unplanned intubation was found to occur with male gender, decreased albumin, increased creatinine, and decreased hematocrit. These were similar findings in the literature review in that those more likely to develop unplanned intubation after thoracic surgery were found to have decreased albumin and hematocrit and increased creatinine (Burton et al., 2018; Li et al., 2018; Ruan et al., 2021). This constellation of factors may be indicative of poor preoperative functional or nutritional status. Given that major surgery results in a decline in functional and physiologic capacity (Burton et al., 2018), patients with a preexisting decline may not be able to withstand the additional burden of major surgery.

Failure to wean risk decreased by 41% with a one-unit (g/dL) increase in albumin, and a one-unit (%) increase in hematocrit was correlated to an 8% decreased risk. One study that looked specifically at patient factors that may affect weaning outcomes (Wu et al., 2019) found albumin to be a useful factor for predicting weaning outcomes. However, this study underlines that little is known regarding the exact mechanism of how albumin affects weaning failure or success. Increased albumin could indicate adequate blood volume, leading to appropriate preload and cardiac output, which will allow more optimal oxygen delivery. Furthermore, increased hematocrit can indicate increased oxygen-carrying capacity, thus, potentially increasing oxygen delivery as well.

Our analysis was able to correlate a) the risk for pulmonary embolism with decreased albumin and increased hematocrit; b) the risk for pneumonia with decreased albumin; c) the risk for unplanned intubation risk with increased creatinine, decreased hematocrit and albumin and male gender; and d) the risk of failure to wean from mechanical intubation with a decreased

albumin and decreased hematocrit. The full model had the highest degree of significance for failure to wean, unplanned intubation, and pneumonia respectively ($p < .0001$). This indicates that the preoperative variables (gender, albumin, creatinine, hematocrit, BMI) could have a cumulative effect on the development of each of the stated three APROs. BMI was not significantly associated with observing any of the APROs. This was an unexpected finding in that the literature review found that BMI < 25 placed a person at risk for APROs (Ruan et al., 2021). Decreased albumin was a significant risk factor for all four APROs independently. Previous literature has correlated decreased albumin to the generalized development of non-specific postoperative complications. However, this is the first study to correlate four specific APROs with decreased albumin. This finding is useful in knowing that albumin levels may impact the development of any of the four specific APROs and may be beneficial to optimize and increase albumin prior to surgery.

Recommendations

Findings from this study may be useful for future research and practice. The results from this study could be used as a starting point in analyzing and narrowing down outcomes on a specific APRO in a future study. Additional studies are recommended to increase the years for which NSQIP data is observed. This will allow for more cases to be analyzed and evaluated. Should further research continue to support the findings of gender, BMI, creatinine, albumin, and hematocrit as predictors for APROs, it is recommended that a preoperative checklist or risk assessment tool be developed and implemented. Additionally, given that this project utilized the Iowa Model as the supporting framework, it is also recommended that any efforts towards dissemination, additional research, and implementation in future practice utilize the Iowa Implementation for Sustainability Framework.

Implications

The results of the data analyzed may be beneficial to assess lab values in individuals undergoing thoracic surgery to evaluate the risk of developing an APRO. Given the significant correlation to all four APROs, this may be especially true for serum albumin. Results from this study could be used in developing a preoperative checklist or risk assessment tool for patients undergoing thoracic surgery to assess the risk of developing an APRO postoperatively.

Limitations

One limitation of this study is that only NSQIP data from 2021 was analyzed. Expanding the search criteria to more years may yield different and more findings. 2021 was also the year that a pandemic occurred due to SARS-COVID-19. Multiple surgeries were canceled or postponed in 2021, which could have yielded potentially significant data. Additionally, the current study could not analyze certain variables, such as frailty and preoperative serum lactate values, because they were not included in the NSQIP database. Selection bias was another limitation as participation was voluntary, an ACS-trained hospital surgical clinical reviewer was needed to collect data, and a disproportionate contribution to NSQIP has been made from larger teaching hospitals. This selection bias may not produce a representative population for all patients undergoing thoracic surgery as the NSQIP database, due to its criteria for inclusion, prevents every hospital in the country from providing data. Another limitation is that the NSQIP database does not track APROs that occur beyond 30 days postoperatively (Zhong et al., 2022). Thus, APROs occurring outside this window were not recognized in the analysis. Lastly, utilizing the NSQIP database does not allow for the inclusion of variables that may be different from facility to facility (Zhong et al., 2022). Therefore, the potential for confounding factors not presented in this paper may be present.

Conclusions

The findings in this study are relevant due to the incidence of APROs that occur after thoracic surgery. As discussed, morbidity, healthcare cost, and LOS are heavily influenced by APROs (Blanc et al., 2018; Fleisher & Linde-Zwirble, 2014; Miskovic & Lumb, 2017). The results from the secondary analysis of the NSQIP database on APROs can be used as a steppingstone for additional research. The data presented showed a strong correlation between the five preoperative risk factors and the development of APRO in patients undergoing thoracic surgery. Collectively, the predictors of gender, BMI, creatinine, albumin, and hematocrit correlate to at least one APRO (unplanned intubation, pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, or failure to wean from mechanical ventilation) and serum albumin independently showing strong correlation to the APRO pneumonia. Not only was this study able to solidify previously found data in research to be true, but it was also able to link preoperative hypoalbuminemia and preoperative hematocrit to multiple APROs. However, it is still suggested that a further look into additional APROs and predictors be conducted, as it will benefit the safety of future patients and providers.

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Appendix A

The Iowa Model Revised

The Iowa Model Revised

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Appendix B**Table 1: Project Timeline***Project Timeline*

Task	Proposed Date
Proposal Defense: Initial Defense	December 2022
IRB Approval from Both CSUF & KPSA	1st Quarter of 2023
Complete a Statistical Analysis of the Data	2nd Quarter of 2023
Analyze Findings	2nd & 3rd Quarter of 2023
Presentation of Findings: Final Defense	December 2023

Appendix C

Table 2: Evaluation and Measurement of Outcomes

Evaluation and Measurement of Outcomes

Outcome	Operation Definition	Method of Measurement	Analysis
Explore relationships between preoperative albumin, hematocrit, creatinine, BMI, and gender and the occurrence of unplanned intubation, pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, and prolonged mechanical ventilation >48 hours	Negative, positive, or no correlation between defined variables and APROs	NSQIP database	Correlational test
Identify predictors of unplanned intubation, pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, and prolonged mechanical ventilation >48 hours	Confirmation or rejection of identified variables as predictors of APROs	NSQIP database	Multivariate logistic regression
Creation of practice guidelines	List of practice guidelines detailing which of the identified variables serve as predictors of APROs	Completion of final DNP Project	Dissemination of study results

Appendix D

Table 3: CPT Codes

CPT Codes

Code	Procedure
15260	Full thickness graft, free, including direct closure of donor site, nose, ears, eyelids, and/or lips; 20 sq cm or less
15734	Muscle, myocutaneous or fasciocutaneous flap; trunk
21501	Incision and drainage, deep abscess or hematoma, soft tissues of neck of thorax
21502	Incision and drainage, deep abscess or hematoma, soft tissues of neck of thorax; with partial rib ostectomy
21510	Incision, deep, with opening of bone cortex (eg, for osteomyelitis or bone abscess), thorax
21600	Excision of rib, partial
21601	Excision of chest wall tumor including rib(s)
21615	Excision first and/or cervical rib;
21620	Ostectomy of sternum, partial
21743	Reconstructive repair of pectus excavatum or carinatum; minimally invasive approach (Nuss procedure), with thoracoscopy
21811	Open treatment of rib fracture(s) with internal fixation, includes thoracoscopic visualization when performed, unilateral; 1-3 ribs
21825	Open treatment of sternum fracture with or without skeletal fixation
21899	Unlisted procedure, neck or thorax
22551	Arthrodesis, anterior interbody, including disc space preparation, discectomy, osteophytectomy and decompression of spinal cord and/or nerve roots; cervical below C2
22633	Arthrodesis, combined posterior or posterolateral technique with posterior interbody technique including laminectomy and/or discectomy sufficient to prepare interspace (other than for decompression), single interspace; lumbar
23044	Arthrotomy, acromioclavicular, sternoclavicular joint, including exploration, drainage or removal of foreign body
23106	Arthrotomy, sternoclavicular joint, with synovectomy, with or without biopsy
23120	Claviclectomy; partial
23170	Sequestrectomy (eg, for osteomyelitis or bone abscess); clavicle
27130	Arthroplasty, acetabular and proximal femoral prosthetic replacement, (total hip arthroplasty), with or without autograft or allograft
27447	Arthroplasty, knee, condyle and plateau; medial AND lateral compartments with or without patella resurfacing (total knee replacement)
31760	Tracheoplasty; intrathoracic
31770	Bronchoplasty; graft repair
31780	Excision tracheal stenosis and anastomosis; cervical
31785	Excision of tracheal tumor or carcinoma; cervical
31825	Surgical closure tracheostomy or fistula; with plastic repair
31899	Unlisted procedure, trachea, bronchi

Code	Procedure
32035	Thoracostomy; with rib resection for empyema
32036	Thoracostomy; with open flap drainage for empyema
32096	Thoracotomy, with diagnostic biopsy(ies) of lung infiltrate(s) (eg wedge, incisional), unilateral
32097	Thoracotomy, with diagnostic biopsy(ies) of lung nodule(s) or mass(es) (eg wedge, incisional), unilateral
32098	Thoracotomy, with biopsy(ies) of pleura
32100	Thoracotomy; with exploration
32110	Thoracotomy; with control of traumatic hemorrhage and/or repair of lung tear
32124	Thoracotomy; with open intrapleural pneumonolysis
32140	Thoracotomy; with cyst(s) removal, includes pleural procedure when performed
32141	Thoracotomy; with resection-plication of bullae, includes any pleural procedure when performed
32150	Thoracotomy; with removal of intrapleural foreign body or fibrin deposit
32200	Pneumonostomy; with open drainage of abscess or cyst
32215	Pleural scarification for repeat pneumothorax
32220	Decortication, pulmonary (separate procedure); total
32225	Decortication, pulmonary (separate procedure); partial
32310	Pleurectomy; parietal (separate procedure)
32320	Decortication and parietal pleurectomy
32440	Removal of lung, pneumonectomy
32480	Removal of lung, other than pneumonectomy; single lobe (lobectomy)
32482	Removal of lung, other than pneumonectomy; two lobes (bilobectomy)
32484	Removal of lung, other than pneumonectomy; single segment (segmentectomy)
32486	Removal of lung, other than pneumonectomy; with circumferential resection of segment of bronchus followed by broncho-bronchial, anastomosis (sleeve lobectomy)
32504	Resection of apical lung tumor (eg, Pancoast tumor), including chest wall resection, rib(s) resection(s), neurovascular dissection, when performed
32505	Thoracotomy; with therapeutic wedge resection (eg, mass, nodule) initial
32663	Thoracoscopy, surgical; with lobectomy (single lobe)
32666	Thoracoscopy, surgical; with therapeutic wedge resection (eg, mass, nodule), initial unilateral
32668	Thoracoscopy, surgical; with diagnostic wedge resection followed by anatomic lung resection
32669	Thoracoscopy, surgical; with removal of a single lung segment (segmentectomy)
43107	Total or near esophagectomy, without thoracotomy; with pharyngogastrostomy or cervical esophagogastrostomy, with or without pyloroplasty (transhiatal)

Code	Procedure
43112	Total or near total esophagectomy, with thoracotomy; with pharyngogastrostomy or cervical esophagogastrostomy, with or without pyloroplasty
43117	Partial esophagectomy, distal 2/3, with thoracotomy and separate abdominal incision, with or without proximal gastrectomy; with thoracic esophagogastrostomy, with or without pyloroplasty (Ivor Lewis)
43118	Partial esophagectomy, distal 2/3, with thoracotomy and separate abdominal incision, with or without proximal gastrectomy; with colon interposition or small intestine reconstruction, including intestine mobilization, preparation, and anastomosis(es)
43287	Esophagectomy, distal two-thirds, with laparoscopic mobilization of the abdominal and lower mediastinal esophagus and proximal gastrectomy, with laparoscopic pyloric drainage procedure if performed, with separate thoracoscopic mobilization of the middle and upper mediastinal esophagus and thoracic esophagogastrostomy (ie, laparoscopic thoracoscopic esophagectomy, Ivor Lewis esophagectomy)
43288	Esophagectomy, total or near total, with thoracoscopic mobilization of the upper, middle and lower mediastinal esophagus, with separate laparoscopic proximal gastrectomy, with laparoscopic pyloric drainage procedure if performed, with open cervical pharyngogastrostomy or esophagogastrostomy (ie, thoracoscopic, laparoscopic and cervical incision esophagectomy, McKeown esophagectomy, tri-incisional esophagectomy)

Appendix E

Table 4: Summative VIF Table

Summative VIF Table

Variable	Pneumonia	Failure to Wean	Unplanned Intubation	Pulmonary Embolism
Sex	1.04058	1.04551	1.02881	1.20385
BMI	1.02275	1.01402	1.01927	1.04385
Preoperative Creatinine	1.06155	1.05936	1.06992	1.25324
Preoperative Albumin	1.43366	1.57674	1.30397	1.56604
Preoperative Hematocrit	1.50514	1.68343	1.40175	1.47759

Appendix F

Table 5: Summative APRO Table

Summative APRO Table

APRO	Predictors	<i>B</i>	Odds Ratio	95% Confidence Interval Limit
Pulmonary Embolism	Sex	-.51	.60	.15 - 2.39
	BMI	.06	1.06	.98 - 1.15
	Creatinine	.46	1.58	.14 - 17.69
	Albumin*	- 1.36	.25	.08 - .82
	Hematocrit*	.22	1.25	1.05 - 1.48
Pneumonia	Sex	.20	1.22	.89 - 1.69
	BMI	-.02	.98	.96 - 1.01
	Creatinine	.12	1.13	.92 - 1.39
	Albumin*	-.58	.56	.42 - .74
	Hematocrit	-.03	.97	.94 - 1.00
Unplanned Intubations	Sex*	.64	1.89	1.08 - 3.32
	BMI	.00	1.00	.97 - 1.04
	Creatinine*	.45	1.57	1.05 - 2.35
	Albumin*	-.80	.45	.27 - .76
	Hematocrit*	-.06	.95	.90 - 1.00
Failure to Wean	Sex	.11	1.11	.64 - 1.95
	BMI	.00	1.00	.96 - 1.05
	Creatinine	.06	1.06	.83 - 1.35
	Albumin*	-.53	.59	.37 - .93
	Hematocrit*	-.08	.92	.88 - .98

Note. * $p < .05$